

FURYE QATORI. FUNKSIYALARNI FURYE QATORIGA YOYISH

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KALIT SO'ZLAR

Furye qatori, Furye koeffitsiyentlari.

Funksiyalarni Furye qatoriga yoyish.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada matematikaning eng muhim mavzularidan biri bo'lgan Furye qatori. Funksiyani Furye qatoriga yoyish tog'risida malumot keltirildi va mavjud muanmolar xal etildi. Agar $f(x)$ funksiya $[a;b]$ kesmada monoton bo'lsa yoki $[a;b]$ kesmani chekli sondagi qisman kesmalarga bo'lish mumkin bo'lsa va bu kesmalarning har birida $f(x)$ funksiya monoton (faqat o'ssa yoki faqat kamaysa) yoki o'zgarmas bo'lsa, $f(x)$ funksiyaga $[a;b]$ kesmada bo'laklimonoton funksiya deyiladi. Agar $f(x)$ funksiya $[a;b]$ kesmada chekli sondagi birinchi tur uzilish nuqtalariga ega bo'lsa, $f(x)$ funksiyaga $[a;b]$ kesmada bo'lakli-uzluksiz funksiya deyiladi. Agar $f(x)$ funksiya $[a;b]$ kesmada uzluksiz yoki bo'lakli-uzluksiz bo'lib, bo'lakli-monoton bo'lsa $f(x)$ funksiya $[a;b]$ kesmada Dirixle shartlarini qanoatlantiradi deyiladi.

1. Furye qatori .

Faraz qilaylik, $f(x)$ funksiya $R = (-\infty, +\infty)$ da berilgan bo'lsin. Ma'lumki, shunday $T \in R \setminus \{0\}$ son topilsaki, $\forall x \in R$ da

$$f(x+T) = f(x)$$

tenglik bajarilsa, $f(x)$ davriy funksiya, $T \neq 0$ son esa uning davri deyiladi.

Agar $T \neq 0$ son $f(x)$ funksiyaning davri bo'lsa, u holda

$$kT \quad (k = \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots)$$

sonlar ham shu funksiyaning davri bo'ladi.

Agar $f(x)$ va $g(x)$ davriy funksiyalar bo'lib, $T \neq 0$ ularning davri bo'lsa,

$$f(x) \pm g(x), \quad f(x) \cdot g(x), \quad \frac{f(x)}{g(x)} \quad (g(x) \neq 0)$$

funksiyalar ham davriy bo'lib, ularning davri T ga teng bo'ladi.

$$y = \sin x, \quad y = \cos x \quad \text{funksiyalar} \quad T = 2\pi$$

davriy funksiya bo'lgan holda ushbu

$$\varphi(x) = a \cos \alpha x + b \sin \alpha x \quad (a, b, \alpha -$$

o'zgarmas, $\alpha \neq 0$)

funksiya ham davriy funksiya bo'lib, uning

davri $T = \frac{2\pi}{\alpha}$ bo'ladi. Haqiqatan ham,

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi\left(x + \frac{2\pi}{\alpha}\right) &= a \cos\left[\alpha\left(x + \frac{2\pi}{\alpha}\right)\right] + b \sin\left[\alpha\left(x + \frac{2\pi}{\alpha}\right)\right] = \\ &= a \cos(\alpha x + 2\pi) + b \sin(\alpha x + 2\pi) = a \cos \alpha x + b \sin \alpha x = \varphi(x) \end{aligned}$$

bo'ladi.

Bu $\varphi(x) = a \cos \alpha x + b \sin \alpha x$ sodda davriy funksiya bo'lib, u garmonika deb ataladi.

Aytaylik, $f(x)$ funksiya $[-\pi, \pi]$ da uzluksiz bo'lsin.

Unda $f(x) \cos nx, f(x) \sin nx \quad (n = 1, 2, 3, \dots)$

funksiyalar ham $[-\pi, \pi]$ da uzluksiz bo'lib, ular $[-\pi, \pi]$ da integrallanuvchi bo'ladi. Bu integrallarni quyidagicha belgilaymiz:

$$a_0 = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) dx,$$

$$a_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \cos nx dx, \quad (n=1, 2, \dots) \quad (1)$$

$$b_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \sin nx dx. \quad (n=1, 2, \dots)$$

Bu sonlardan foydalanib, ushbu

$$\frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \cos nx + b_n \sin nx) \quad (2)$$

qatorni (uni trigonometrik qator deyiladi) hosil qilamiz.

(2) qator funksional qator bo'lib, uning har bir hadi garmonikadan iborat.

Ta'rif. (2) funksional qator $f(x)$ funksiyaning Furye qatori deyiladi. (1) munosabatlar bilan aniqlangan

$$a_0, a_1, b_1, a_2, b_2, \dots, a_n, b_n, \dots$$

sonlar Furye koeffitsiyentlari deyiladi.

7.2. Funksiyalarni Furye qatoriga yoyish.

Demak, berilgan $f(x)$ funksiyaning Furye koeffitsiyentlari shu funksiyaga bog'liq bo'lib, (2) formulalar yordamida aniqlanadi, qator esa quyidagicha:

$$f(x) \sim \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \cos nx + b_n \sin nx).$$

belgilanadi.

1-misol. Ushbu $f(x) = e^{\alpha x}$ ($-\pi \leq x \leq \pi, \alpha \neq 0$)

funksiyaning Furye qatori topilsin.

◀ (1) formulalardan foydalanib, berilgan funksiyaning Furye koeffitsiyentlarini hisoblaymiz:

$$a_0 = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} e^{\alpha x} dx = \frac{1}{\alpha \pi} (e^{\alpha \pi} - e^{-\alpha \pi}) = \frac{2}{\alpha \pi} \operatorname{sh} \alpha \pi,$$

$$a_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} e^{\alpha x} \cos nx dx = \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{\alpha \cos nx + n \sin nx}{\alpha^2 + n^2} e^{\alpha x} \Big|_{-\pi}^{\pi} =$$

$$= (-1)^n \frac{1}{\pi} \cdot \frac{2\alpha}{\alpha^2 + n^2} \operatorname{sh} \alpha \pi \quad (n=1, 2, \dots),$$

$$b_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} e^{\alpha x} \sin nx dx = \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{\alpha \sin nx - n \cos nx}{\alpha^2 + n^2} e^{\alpha x} \Big|_{-\pi}^{\pi} =$$

$$= (-1)^{n-1} \frac{1}{\pi} \cdot \frac{2n}{\alpha^2 + n^2} \operatorname{sh} \alpha \pi \quad (n=1, 2, \dots).$$

Demak,

$f(x) = e^{\alpha x}$ funksiyaning Furye qatori

$$f(x) = e^{\alpha x} \sim \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \cos nx + b_n \sin nx) =$$

$$= \frac{2 \operatorname{sh} \alpha \pi}{\pi} \left[\frac{1}{2\alpha} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{\alpha^2 + n^2} (\alpha \cos nx - n \sin nx) \right]$$

bo'ladi. ▶

Aytaylik, $f(x)$ funksiya $[-\pi, \pi]$ da berilgan juft funksiya bo'lsin: $f(-x) = f(x)$. U holda

$f(x) \cdot \cos nx$ juft, $f(x) \cdot \sin nx$ toq ($n=1, 2, 3, \dots$) funksiya bo'ladi.

(1) formulalardan foydalanib, $f(x)$ funksiyaning Furye koeffitsiyentlarini topamiz:

$$a_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \cos nx dx = \frac{1}{\pi} \left[\int_{-\pi}^0 f(x) \cos nx dx + \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \cos nx dx \right] =$$

$$= \frac{1}{\pi} \left[\int_0^{\pi} f(x) \cos nx dx + \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \cos nx dx \right] =$$

$$\frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \cos nx dx \quad (n=0, 1, 2, \dots).$$

$$b_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \sin nx dx = \frac{1}{\pi} \left[\int_{-\pi}^0 f(x) \sin nx dx + \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \sin nx dx \right] =$$

$$= \frac{1}{\pi} \left[-\int_0^{\pi} f(x) \sin nx dx + \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \sin nx dx \right] = 0 \quad (n=1, 2, \dots).$$

Demak, juft $f(x)$ funksiyaning Furye koeffitsiyentlari

$$a_n = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \cos nx dx \quad (n=0, 1, 2, \dots)$$

$$b_n = 0 \quad (n=1, 2, \dots)$$

bo'lib, Furye qatori

$$f(x) \sim \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \cos nx$$

bo'ladi.

Aytaylik, $f(x)$ funksiya $[-\pi, \pi]$ da berilgan toq funksiya bo'lsin:

$$f(-x) = -f(x). \text{ U holda}$$

$$f(x) \cdot \cos nx \quad \text{toq}, \quad f(x) \cdot \sin nx \quad \text{juft} \\ (n = 1, 2, 3, \dots) \text{ funksiya bo'ladi.}$$

(1) formulalardan foydalanib, $f(x)$ funksiyaning Furye koeffitsiyentlarini topamiz:

$$a_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \cos nx dx = \frac{1}{\pi} \left[\int_{-\pi}^0 f(x) \cos nx dx + \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \cos nx dx \right] = \\ = \frac{1}{\pi} \left[- \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \cos nx dx + \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \cos nx dx \right] = 0 \quad (n = 0, 1, 2, \dots),$$

$$b_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \sin nx dx = \frac{1}{\pi} \left[\int_{-\pi}^0 f(x) \sin nx dx + \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \sin nx dx \right] = \\ = \frac{2}{\pi} \left[\int_0^{\pi} f(x) \sin nx dx \right] \quad (n = 1, 2, \dots).$$

Demak, toq $f(x)$ funksiyaning Furye koeffitsiyentlari

$$a_n = 0, \quad (n = 0, 1, 2, \dots),$$

$$b_n = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \sin nx dx, \quad (n = 1, 2, \dots)$$

bo'lib, Furye qatori

$$f(x) \sim \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n \sin nx$$

bo'ladi.

2-misol. Ushbu

$$f(x) = x^2 \quad (-\pi \leq x \leq \pi)$$

juft funksiyaning Furye qatori topilsin.

◀ Avvalo berilgan funksiyaning Furye koeffitsiyentlarini topamiz:

$$a_0 = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x^2 dx = \frac{2}{3} \pi^2,$$

$$a_n = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x^2 \cos nx dx = \frac{2}{\pi} x^2 \frac{\sin nx}{n} \Big|_0^{\pi} - \frac{4}{n\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x \sin nx dx = \\ = \frac{4}{\pi n} \left(\frac{x \cos nx}{n} \Big|_0^{\pi} - \frac{1}{n} \int_0^{\pi} \cos nx dx \right) = (-1)^n \cdot \frac{4}{n^2} \cdot (n = 1, 2, \dots)$$

Demak, $f(x) = x^2$ funksiyaning Furye qatori

$$f(x) = x^2 \sim \frac{\pi^2}{3} + 4 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{\cos nx}{n^2}$$

bo'ladi. ▶

3-misol. Ushbu

$$f(x) = x \quad (-\pi \leq x \leq \pi)$$

toq funksiyaning Furye qatori topilsin.

◀ Berilgan funksiyaning Furye koeffitsiyentlarini hisoblaymiz:

$$b_n = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x \sin nx dx = \frac{2}{\pi} \left(-\frac{x \cos nx}{n} \Big|_0^{\pi} + \frac{1}{n} \int_0^{\pi} \cos nx dx \right) = \frac{2(-1)^{n-1}}{n}$$

Demak, $f(x) = x$ funksiyaning Furye qatori

$$f(x) \sim \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n-1} \frac{2}{n} \sin nx \text{ bo'ladi. } \blacktriangleright$$

Faraz qilaylik, $f(x)$ funksiya $[-p, p]$ ($p > 0$) segmentda uzluksiz bo'lsin.

Ma'lumki, ushbu

$$t = \frac{\pi}{p} x$$

almashtirish $[-p, p]$ oraliqni $[-\pi, \pi]$ ga o'tkazadi, ya'ni x o'zgaruvchi $[-p, p]$ da o'zgaranda t o'zgaruvchi $[-\pi, \pi]$ da o'zgaradi. Endi

$$f(x) = f\left(\frac{p}{\pi} t\right) = \varphi(t).$$

deymiz. Unda $\varphi(t)$ funksiya $[-\pi, \pi]$ oraliqda berilgan uzluksiz funksiya bo'ladi. Bu funksiyaning Furye koeffitsiyentlari

$$a_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \varphi(t) \cos ntdt, \quad (n = 0, 1, 2, \dots)$$

$$b_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \varphi(t) \sin ntdt \quad (n = 1, 2, \dots)$$

ni topib, Furye qatorini yozamiz:

$$\varphi(t) \sim \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \cos nt + b_n \sin nt).$$

Modomiki,

$$t = \frac{\pi}{p} x$$

ekan, unda

$$\varphi\left(\frac{\pi}{p} x\right) \sim \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(a_n \cos n \frac{\pi}{p} x + b_n \sin n \frac{\pi}{p} x \right),$$

bo'lib, uning koeffitsiyentlari

$$a_n = \frac{1}{p} \int_{-p}^p \varphi\left(\frac{\pi}{p} x\right) \cos n \frac{\pi}{p} x dx, \quad (n=0, 1, 2, \dots)$$

$$b_n = \frac{1}{p} \int_{-p}^p \varphi\left(\frac{\pi}{p} x\right) \sin n \frac{\pi}{p} x dx. \quad (n=1, 2, \dots)$$

bo'ladi. Natijada $[-p, p]$ da berilgan $f(x)$

funksiyaning Furye qatorini quyidagicha

$$f(x) \sim \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(a_n \cos \frac{n\pi x}{p} + b_n \sin \frac{n\pi x}{p} \right)$$

bo'lishini topamiz, bunda

$$a_n = \frac{1}{p} \int_{-p}^p f(x) \cos \frac{n\pi x}{p} dx \quad (n=0, 1, 2, \dots)$$

$$b_n = \frac{1}{p} \int_{-p}^p f(x) \sin \frac{n\pi x}{p} dx \quad (n=1, 2, \dots)$$

4-misol. Ushbu

$$f(x) = e^x \quad (-1 \leq x \leq 1)$$

funksiyaning Furye qatori topilsin.

◀ Yuqoridagi formulalardan foydalanib,

$$f(x) = e^x \quad \text{funksiyaning Furye}$$

koeffitsiyentlarini topamiz:

$$a_0 = \int_{-1}^1 e^x dx = e - e^{-1}, \quad a_n = \int_{-1}^1 e^x \cos n\pi x dx = \frac{n\pi \sin n\pi x - \cos n\pi x}{1+n^2\pi^2} e^x \Big|_{-1}^1 =$$

$$= \frac{1}{1+n^2\pi^2} (e \cos n\pi - e^{-1} \cos n\pi) = (-1)^n \frac{e - e^{-1}}{1+n^2\pi^2} \quad (n=1, 2, \dots),$$

$$b_n = \int_{-1}^1 e^x \sin n\pi x dx = \frac{\sin n\pi x - n\pi \cos n\pi x}{1+n^2\pi^2} e^x \Big|_{-1}^1 =$$

$$= \frac{1}{1+n^2\pi^2} (e n\pi \cos n\pi + n\pi e^{-1} \cos n\pi) =$$

$$= \frac{n\pi (-1)^n}{1+n^2\pi^2} (e^{-1} - e) = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{e - e^{-1}}{1+n^2\pi^2} \quad (n=1, 2, \dots)$$

Demak,

$$f(x) = e^x \quad (-1 \leq x \leq 1)$$

funksiyaning Furye qatori

$$e^x \sim \frac{e - e^{-1}}{2} + (e - e^{-1}) \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(-1)^n}{1+n^2\pi^2} \cos n\pi + \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{1+n^2\pi^2} n\pi \sin n\pi x \right]$$

bo'ladi.▶

Aytaylik, $f(x)$ funksiya $[a, b]$ da berilgan

bo'lsin. $[a, b]$ segment a_k nuqtalar

yordamida bo'laklarga ajratilgan.

($a_0 = a, a_n = b$).

Agar har bir (a_k, a_{k+1}) ($k=0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1$)

da $f(x)$ funksiya differensiallanuvchi

bo'lib, $x = a_k$ nuqtalarda chekli o'ng

$$f'(a_k + 0) \quad (k=0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1),$$

va chap

$$f'(a_k - 0) \quad (k=0, 1, 2, \dots, n)$$

hosilalarga ega bo'lsa, $f(x)$ funksiya $[a, b]$

da bo'lakli-differensiallanuvchi deyiladi.

Endi Furye qatorining yaqinlashuvchi

bo'lishi haqidagi teoremani isbotsiz

keltiramiz.

Teorema. 2π davrli $f(x)$ funksiya $[-\pi, \pi]$

oraligida bo'lakli-differensiallanuvchi bo'lsa,

u holda bu funksiyaning Furye qatori

$$f(x) \sim \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (a_k \cos kx + b_k \sin kx)$$

$[-\pi, \pi]$ da yaqinlashuvchi bo'lib, uning

yig'indisi

$$\frac{f(x+0) + f(x-0)}{2}$$

ga teng bo'ladi.

5-misol. Ushbu

$$f(x) = \cos ax \quad (-\pi \leq x \leq \pi, a \neq n \in Z)$$

funksiyaning Furye qatori topilsin va u

yaqinlashishga tekshirilsin.

◀ Bu funksiyaning Furye koeffitsiyentlarini

topamiz. Qaralayotgan funksiya juft bo'lgani

uchun

$$b_n = 0 \quad (n=1, 2, 3, \dots)$$

bo'lib,

$$a_n = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} \cos ax \cos nx dx = \int_0^{\pi} [\cos(a-n)x + \cos(a+n)x] dx =$$

$$= \frac{\sin a\pi}{\pi} (-1)^n \left[\frac{1}{a+n} + \frac{1}{a-n} \right]$$

bo'ladi. Demak,

$$f(x) \sim \frac{\sin a\pi}{\pi} \left[\frac{1}{a} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^n \left(\frac{1}{a+n} + \frac{1}{a-n} \right) \cos nx \right]$$

Agar $f(x) = \cos ax$ funksiya teoremaning shartlarini bajarishini e'tiborga olsak, unda

$$\cos ax = \frac{\sin a\pi}{\pi} \left[\frac{1}{a} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^n \left(\frac{1}{a+n} + \frac{1}{a-n} \right) \cos nx \right]$$

bo'lishini topamiz. ►

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